

**EFFECTIVENESS OF THE JIGSAW COOPERATIVE LEARNING STRATEGY IN
PROMOTING STUDENT ENGAGEMENT AND LONG-TERM KNOWLEDGE
RETENTION**

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Abstract:

AIM: To assess the effectiveness of the jigsaw learning method in promoting retention of knowledge and student engagement among second-year nursing students in understanding and reporting of adverse drug reactions (ADRs).

Objectives: To evaluate baseline knowledge, immediate post-session learning, student engagement and knowledge retention at 40 days following a intervention based on jigsaw learning method.

Methods: A quasi-experimental was conducted among 78 second-year nursing students at St. Peter's Nursing College, Hosur. The jigsaw cooperative learning session lasted two hours and focused on understanding and reporting of ADR which included a session on ADR form filling. Students were first introduced to the lesson plan, then assigned to home and expert groups to learn the content through discussion, peer teaching and active collaboration. After mastering the topic, they returned to home groups to share their learning with peers. Knowledge was assessed using pre-test, immediate post-test and 40-day retention test scores. Student engagement was measured using a validated 22-item questionnaire.

Results: The mean pre-test score was 8.40 ± 3.54 , which increased to 14.3 ± 2.15 after the intervention, showing a significant improvement in knowledge. Students demonstrated better understanding of ADR reporting and improved performance in form filling, particularly in suspected ADR and medication details during 40 day retention test. Their perceptions became more favorable after the session, with increased confidence in reporting ADRs and recognition of its importance in nursing practice. Engagement was moderate to high across emotional, behavioral and cognitive domains.

Conclusion: Jigsaw learning method proved to be an effective student-centered strategy for improving knowledge, participation, collaboration and attitude toward ADR and its reporting. It can be effectively integrated into nursing education to promote active learning and strengthen pharmacovigilance practices.

Keywords: Jigsaw learning method, cooperative learning, ADR reporting, pharmacovigilance, nursing students, active learning

Introduction:

The rapid advancement of healthcare systems has increased the need for competent healthcare professionals who possess not only sound theoretical knowledge but also effective communication, teamwork, and problem-solving skills. Traditional lecture-based teaching methods, although effective for delivering information to large groups, often provide limited opportunities for active participation and collaborative learning. Consequently, modern health professions education has increasingly adopted learner-centered and evidence-based teaching approaches that encourage active engagement and deeper understanding of concepts¹⁻⁵.

Cooperative learning is one such educational strategy that has gained considerable attention in medical and nursing education. It is an instructional approach in which students work together in small groups to achieve common learning objectives while supporting each other's learning process. Studies have demonstrated that cooperative learning improves academic achievement, critical thinking, communication skills, student motivation, and overall learning satisfaction when compared with conventional teaching methods⁶⁻¹¹. The theoretical foundation of cooperative learning is rooted in Vygotsky's social constructivist theory, which emphasizes that learning occurs more effectively through social interaction, discussion, and shared experiences¹². Through peer-assisted learning and collaborative knowledge construction, students become active participants in the educational process rather than passive recipients of information.

In contemporary healthcare practice, effective collaboration among healthcare professionals is essential for ensuring patient safety and delivering high-quality care. Most clinical situations require multidisciplinary teamwork, where communication and cooperation among healthcare professionals play a vital role in achieving optimal patient outcomes¹³⁻¹⁶. However, these collaborative competencies are often inadequately developed during traditional educational training. Researchers have suggested that the limited incorporation of structured cooperative learning activities during undergraduate education may contribute to deficiencies in teamwork and collective competence among future healthcare professionals¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Therefore, there is a growing need to integrate educational strategies that promote collaborative learning and teamwork early in professional training

Among the various cooperative learning methods, the Jigsaw technique is recognized as one of the most structured and effective approaches. Developed by Aronson, the Jigsaw method

divides students into small groups where each member becomes an “expert” on a specific component of the topic. Students first discuss and master their assigned content within expert groups and subsequently return to their home groups to teach their peers²⁰⁻²². This process promotes accountability, peer teaching, active participation, communication, and collaborative problem-solving. The role of the facilitator is primarily to guide discussions and ensure effective group functioning rather than directly delivering content²³⁻²⁵. Previous studies have reported that the Jigsaw technique enhances academic performance, student engagement, teamwork, critical thinking, and long-term retention of knowledge among medical and nursing students²⁶⁻³³.

Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) remain a significant public health concern and contribute substantially to patient morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs. Effective pharmacovigilance depends largely on timely identification and reporting of ADRs by healthcare professionals, including nurses. Since nurses are directly involved in patient care and medication administration, adequate knowledge and positive attitudes toward ADR reporting are essential. However, several studies have highlighted deficiencies in pharmacovigilance knowledge and ADR reporting practices among nursing students and healthcare professionals³⁴⁻⁴⁰. Innovative educational approaches that actively engage learners may help overcome these gaps and strengthen pharmacovigilance competencies.

Although the educational benefits of the Jigsaw cooperative learning strategy have been documented in various healthcare disciplines, evidence regarding its effectiveness in teaching ADR reporting and promoting long-term knowledge retention among nursing students remains limited. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the effectiveness of the Jigsaw cooperative learning strategy in improving knowledge, student engagement, attitudes toward ADR reporting, and long-term retention of pharmacovigilance concepts among second-year nursing students.

Objectives

- 1 To assess the baseline knowledge of students regarding adverse drug reactions (ADRs).
- 2 To evaluate immediate post-intervention knowledge following a teaching session on ADRs and ADR form filling.
- 3 To assess long-term knowledge retention of ADR form filling after 40 days of the intervention.

- 4 To evaluate student engagement during the teaching session using a Student Engagement Questionnaire.
- 5 To compare pre-test, immediate post-test, and 40-day retention scores to determine the effectiveness of the intervention.

Methodology :

A quasi-experimental study was conducted among second year nursing students at St.Peter's Nursing college, Hosur. All students present during the intervention, willing to provide informed consent and participate in the study were included in the study. Students who were absent during the intervention were excluded from study.

A pre-test was administered to assess baseline knowledge, classification, monitoring and reporting of Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR) in India. Following the pre-test, students were given an introduction regarding ADR including ADR reporting and ADR form filling.

The students were divided into home groups then into expert groups. Students were initially divided into home group and assigned learning objectives. Later, in the expert group phase students worked collaboratively discussing and mastering assigned topics. Later they moved into their respective home group, where each member taught their topic to peers. Each group was assigned a facilitator to guide through group discussions and peer assisted learning.

An immediate post-test was administered at end of the session to evaluate improvement in knowledge. A student engagement questionnaire was used to evaluate student participation and involvement during the teaching session. A retention test was conducted 40 days after the intervention to assess long-term retention of knowledge related to ADR form filling.

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed by using appropriate statistical methods. Data were analyzed by descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The effectiveness of the intervention was evaluated through comparative analysis of pre-test, post-test and retention test scores. Statistical significance was defined as p-value <0.05. Institutional permission was taken before starting the study. All participants provided written informed consent and participant information was kept confidential throughout the study.

RESULTS

A total of 78 students were included in the analysis. There was no missing data for both pre-test and post-test scores. The mean pre-test knowledge score regarding adverse drug reactions was 8.40 ± 3.54 with a range of 0-16 score. This suggests a moderate baseline knowledge among participants. After the teaching intervention, the mean post-test score was 14.3 ± 2.15 with a range of 7-17 score this shows a significant improvement in knowledge levels. A paired t-test showed a statistically significant pre-test to post-test scores improvement, $t(77) = 14.3$ and $p < 0.001$. The mean score difference was 5.95 ± 0.42 , with a 95% confidence interval of 5.12 to 6.77 which indicates a precise estimate of the effect. The magnitude of improvement was large having an effect size of Cohen's $d = 1.62$ (95% CI: 1.28-1.96). This reflects a strong practical effectiveness of the educational intervention on the students (Table 1).

Table 1: Comparison of pre-test and post-test scores of the students (N = 78)

Comparison	Mean Difference \pm SE	95% CI	t (df)	p-value	Cohen's d
Post – test vs Pre – test	5.95 ± 0.42	5.12 – 6.77	14.3 (77)	<0.001	1.62

Table 2: Comparison of student perceptions on ADR (N = 78)

Student's perception	Response	Pre-test n (%)	Post-test n (%)
ADR reporting is routine in nursing	Strongly Agree	20 (25.6)	38 (48.7)
	Agree	42 (53.8)	37 (47.4)
	Neutral	11 (14.1)	3 (3.9)
	Disagree	3 (3.8)	0 (0.0)
	Strongly Disagree	2 (2.6)	0 (0.0)
Feel confident reporting ADR	Strongly Agree	18 (23.1)	19 (24.4)
	Agree	37 (47.4)	51 (65.4)
	Neutral	14 (17.9)	8 (10.3)
	Disagree	4 (5.1)	0 (0.0)
	Strongly Disagree	5 (6.4)	0 (0.0)
Pharmacovigilance training in nursing	Strongly Agree	24 (30.8)	34 (43.6)
	Agree	28 (35.9)	39 (50.0)
	Neutral	21 (26.9)	4 (5.1)
	Disagree	2 (2.6)	0 (0.0)
	Strongly Disagree	3 (3.8)	1 (1.3)

Table 2 shows the comparison of student's perception towards ADR before and after intervention. There was an improvement in students' perceptions following the educational intervention. For the statement "ADR reporting is routine in nursing," the proportion of students who strongly agreed increased from 25.6% to 48.7%, with a corresponding decline in neutral and negative responses. Similarly, students' confidence in reporting ADRs improved, with the combined proportion of "agree" and "strongly agree" responses increasing from 70.5% in the pre-test to 89.8% in the post-test. Regarding the importance of pharmacovigilance training in nursing, strong agreement increased from 30.8% to 43.6%, while neutral responses decreased substantially.

Figure 1: Average student engagement scores (N = 78)

Student Engagement Questionnaire (22 items):

The questionnaire consists of 22 items assessing three domains of student engagement: Emotional Engagement (8 items), Behavioral Engagement (7 items), and Cognitive Engagement (7 items). Participants rate each item on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1-Strongly Disagree to 5 Strongly Agree). Higher scores indicate greater engagement during the teaching-learning session.

The line graph shows that the students had moderate to high average engagement scores on the 22 items across the learning sessions. The overall mean scores ranged from roughly 3.29 to 3.67 (on a 5-point Likert scale). The average scores were highest for Item 9 (“I listened carefully to the teacher and my peers”) and Item 14 (“I completed all assigned tasks during the session”) indicating high levels of behavioral engagement and active participation of the students. In addition, Item 5 (“I found the learning environment supportive”) and Item 21 (“I paid attention to details in the learning materials”) were rated above average, indicating that students positively perceived the classroom environment and paid attention during learning activities. On the other hand, relatively lower mean scores were found in Item 7 (“I was emotionally invested in the learning process”) and Item 11 (“I asked questions when I had doubts”) suggesting that emotional engagement and questioning behavior were relatively less prominent than other dimensions of engagement. However, all mean scores were above the midpoint of the scale, indicating that students had positive emotional, cognitive, and behavioral engagement during the instructional sessions (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Distribution of students’ responses across the student engagement (N = 78)

The stacked bar chart suggests a positive engagement of students in the learning sessions in general. The majority of responses were ‘Agree’ (4) and ‘Strongly Agree’ (5) for all 22 items.

The findings show higher levels of engagement (emotional, behavioral and cognitive). Students were keen on the topics, discussed, remained engaged, worked with fellow students, and endeavored to understand the lessons. Many students also reported that they reflected on their learning, used knowledge to solve problems, and critically thought about the topics discussed. Nevertheless, a few items generated some neutral responses, but the percentages of disagreement were relatively low. This suggests that the learning environment was generally conducive, motivating, and effective in facilitating active student engagement and meaningful learning experiences (Figure 2). Table 3: Reliability analysis of the student engagement questionnaire (n = 78)

Item	Mean \pm SD	Item–rest correlation	Cronbach's α if item deleted
Q1. I felt interested in the topics discussed	3.60 \pm 1.20	0.754	0.978
Q2. I was enthusiastic about the session	3.40 \pm 1.07	0.816	0.978
Q3. I enjoyed collaborating with my classmates	3.42 \pm 1.40	0.748	0.979
Q4. I felt motivated to participate actively	3.42 \pm 1.19	0.792	0.978
Q5. I found the learning environment supportive	3.64 \pm 1.21	0.840	0.978
Q6. I felt confident to express my opinions	3.51 \pm 1.27	0.765	0.978
Q7. I was emotionally invested in the learning process	3.29 \pm 1.21	0.716	0.979
Q8. The session made me feel more committed to learning	3.47 \pm 1.20	0.865	0.978
Q9. I listened carefully to the teacher and my peers	3.67 \pm 1.10	0.885	0.977
Q10. I actively participated in discussions and activities	3.49 \pm 1.20	0.837	0.978
Q11. I asked questions when I had doubts	3.36 \pm 1.09	0.641	0.979

Q12. I stayed focused throughout the session	3.41 ± 1.23	0.839	0.978
Q13. I helped my classmates understand the topics	3.49 ± 1.20	0.850	0.978
Q14. I completed all assigned tasks during the session	3.65 ± 1.21	0.868	0.977
Q15. I was punctual and prepared for the session	3.54 ± 1.18	0.886	0.977
Q16. I put effort into understanding the topics deeply	3.45 ± 1.24	0.860	0.978
Q17. I tried to relate the content to real-life situations	3.46 ± 1.19	0.847	0.978
Q18. I reflected on what I learned during and after the session	3.45 ± 1.20	0.881	0.977
Q19. I applied what I learned to solve problems or answer questions	3.50 ± 1.19	0.847	0.978
Q20. I tried to think critically about the topics discussed	3.44 ± 1.11	0.861	0.978
Q21. I paid attention to details in the learning materials	3.56 ± 1.25	0.727	0.979
Q22. I was eager to learn beyond what was taught in class	3.38 ± 1.35	0.839	0.978

Table 3 shows the reliability analysis of the 22 items student engagement questionnaire which demonstrated excellent internal consistency reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.979. Item-rest correlations ranged from 0.641 to 0.886, indicating strong correlations between individual items and the overall scale. Cronbach's alpha if item deleted ranged from 0.977 to 0.979, suggesting that removal of any individual item did not significantly improve the reliability of the scale. Therefore, all items were retained for final analysis and contributed meaningfully to the assessment of student engagement.

Figure 3: Mean Scores of ADR Form-Filling Components Among Participants (n = 78)

The mean score was evaluated on 4 domains of patient information, suspected ADR details, suspected medication details and reporter details among 78 participants. The horizontal bar chart shows higher mean scores for participants in documenting suspected ADR details and suspected medication details for Q7 and Q8, implying improved performance in these aspects of ADR form filling. However, relatively lower scores were observed for certain patient information and medication-related items, specifically Q4 and Q12, suggesting potential areas for further reinforcement and training. In the patient information domain, the mean score was highest for Q2 (1.00 ± 0.00) indicating that all participants had 100% accuracy and lowest for Q4 (0.23 ± 0.38). In the suspected ADR domain, Q7 had the best performance of 1.99 ± 0.06 , while Q5 and Q6 had relatively poor mean scores of 0.49 ± 0.08 and 0.47 ± 0.31 , respectively. In the suspected medication domain, relatively higher scores were obtained for Q8 (2.06 ± 0.40), Q15 (0.87 ± 0.34), and Q9 (0.86 ± 0.35), while lower scores were obtained for Q12 (0.43 ± 0.48) and Q11 (0.49 ± 0.48). Reporter detail items adequately performed with mean scores of 0.74 ± 0.44 for Q16 and 0.59 ± 0.50 for Q17. In general, the average ADR total score of 13.9 reflects a satisfactory competency in ADR form documentation among the participants post-intervention (Figure 3). The long term knowledge after a 40 day retention test was 69.5 percent for ADR form filling.

Discussion:

The present study showed that a structured jigsaw cooperative learning intervention significantly improved second-year nursing students' knowledge and skills regarding adverse drug reactions (ADRs), ADR reporting, and ADR form filling³². Mean knowledge scores increased significantly from pre-test to immediate post -test, with a large effect size (Cohen's $d = 1.62$), confirming the short-term efficacy of this learner-centered approach^{32,33}. These findings are in line with earlier studies in health-profession education where cooperative and jigsaw-based strategies improved academic achievement, conceptual understanding, and higher-order cognitive skills compared with traditional teaching^{5,7,24,29,30}. Recent work in pharmacology further suggests that jigsaw-type cooperative learning compared to conventional small-group teaching can promote immediate learning and long-term retention, highlighting its suitability for content-dense disciplines such as pharmacology and pharmacovigilance^{24,29,31,36,41}.

Our results extend previous evidence on the benefits of jigsaw for cognitive skills, teamwork and collective competence in medical training by applying it early in nursing education in the specific context of pharmacovigilance, where the literature remains relatively sparse^{5, 17, 18, 24, 29, 35, 36}. The significant knowledge gains and satisfactory ADR form-filling performance in our cohort indicate that early, structured cooperative exposure can create a strong foundation for later clinical training, moving learners away from teacher-centered didactic methods toward active knowledge construction and deeper engagement^{1,5,21,22,24}. Forty-day retention scores suggesting that the jigsaw-based session supported meaningful learning rather than transient recall, consistent with reports that cooperative techniques enhance long-term retention and knowledge transfer^{24,29,30,31,41}.

Student engagement data in our study revealed moderate to high emotional, behavioral and cognitive engagement across all 22 items, with particularly high scores for careful listening, task completion, focus and peer support, and an excellent internal consistency for the questionnaire (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.979$)³². These observations echo prior work linking cooperative and jigsaw learning with increased participation, motivation, peer interaction and a more supportive learning climate in health-profession education^{7,10,11,19,24,28,29}.

Although emotional investment and questioning behavior scored slightly lower than other dimensions, all mean scores exceeded the scale midpoint, indicating generally positive engagement. This pattern suggests that while students were comfortable collaborating and following through on tasks, they may still require explicit coaching in reflective dialogue and questioning, which is consistent with reports that early-year learners often need scaffolding to fully exploit interactive methods^{5,19,20,28}.

Beyond cognitive outcomes, the intervention positively shifted students' attitudes, with more participants agreeing that ADR reporting is a routine part of nursing, expressing greater confidence to report, and recognizing the importance of pharmacovigilance training^{37,40}. These attitudinal changes are important because lack of knowledge, low confidence, and negative perceptions are well-documented barriers to ADR reporting among nurses and other healthcare professionals³⁸⁻⁴⁰. Educational and workshop-based interventions in pharmacovigilance have been shown in systematic reviews and meta-analyses to increase ADR reporting rates and pharmacovigilance knowledge, supporting the practical relevance of embedding such teaching early in the curriculum^{37-39,42}. By targeting both knowledge and attitudes, our jigsaw-based session may help address under-reporting driven by uncertainty, fear of legal consequences, or perceived lack of time, thereby aligning with broader patient-safety and pharmacovigilance goals³⁷⁻⁴⁰.

Domain-specific analysis of ADR form-filling performance showed strengths in documenting suspected ADRs and suspected medication details, likely reflecting the clarity of role allocation within expert groups and the emphasis on reaction–drug linkage during discussions³². Conversely, weaker performance in certain patient information and medication fields points to residual gaps, possibly due to the complexity of the form, limited prior exposure to pharmacovigilance documentation and uncertainty about the clinical relevance of some fields³⁹⁻⁴⁰. Previous pharmacovigilance studies among nurses and other professionals have similarly highlighted incomplete or inaccurate ADR forms, particularly for patient demographics, concomitant medications and follow-up information, and have recommended repeated training, structured checklists and supervised practice to improve documentation quality^{38-40,42}. In our context, follow-up sessions using real or

simulated clinical vignettes, along with feedback on sample forms, may further consolidate these competencies and enhance completeness and accuracy of reporting.

The value of the jigsaw technique in this study is particularly evident given typical early-year challenges with group dynamics, such as unequal participation, dominance by a few students or reluctance to speak in front of peers^{5,19,20}. By clearly defining expert and home-group roles, assigning specific subtopics, and ensuring faculty facilitation, the intervention helped distribute responsibility and accountability, minimizing free-riding and encouraging quieter students to contribute^{1,5,21,22,24}. This structure is firmly rooted in Vygotsky's social constructivism, wherein learning is mediated through social interaction and scaffolding, and cooperative learning acts as a catalyst for the co-construction of knowledge, communication skills, and professional identity^{10,12,19,24}. Emerging evidence in nursing education also indicates that integrating jigsaw with self-regulated learning instruction can improve self-regulation, commitment, and confidence, further supporting its use as a multifaceted strategy rather than merely a group-work format^{8,11,26,41}.

From a broader pharmacovigilance perspective, enhancing ADR-related knowledge and confidence early in training is likely to translate into better patient safety and more robust reporting behavior once students transition into clinical practice³⁷⁻⁴⁰. Several studies and recent meta-analyses have demonstrated that structured educational interventions for nurses and other health-care workers significantly improve both pharmacovigilance knowledge and ADR reporting rates, especially when interactive methods and workshops are used, as opposed to passive lectures alone^{37-39,42}. Our findings suggest that jigsaw-based cooperative learning can serve as a practical, low-resource variant of such interactive interventions, particularly in settings with constraints on faculty numbers, as the method leverages peer teaching to distribute instructional load^{1,21-23}. Embedding this approach into pharmacology and nursing curricula may therefore support national pharmacovigilance programs by cultivating a workforce that perceives ADR reporting as a routine, integral component of professional practice rather than an optional task.

Strengths and Limitations:

A major strength of this study is its quasi-experimental design with pre-test, immediate post-test and 40-day retention assessment, allowing evaluation of both immediate and short-term sustained effects of the intervention on knowledge and skills. The use of a validated, internally consistent student engagement questionnaire adds process rigor by capturing emotional, behavioral, and cognitive dimensions of engagement rather than relying solely on performance metrics. Focusing specifically on ADR reporting and form filling—an area frequently cited as deficient among nurses—enhances the clinical relevance of the intervention and aligns with priorities of pharmacovigilance programs in India and globally.

However, certain limitations should be acknowledged. Generalizability is limited because the study was conducted in a single institution with a relatively small cohort of second-year nursing students, and contextual factors such as institutional culture or prior exposure to active learning may have influenced outcomes. The absence of a parallel control group (e.g., lecture or conventional small-group discussion) precludes firm causal attribution to the jigsaw method alone, although results are consistent with comparative studies showing superiority of jigsaw over traditional methods in health-profession education. In addition, the study evaluated knowledge, engagement, and simulated ADR form-filling, but did not assess actual ADR reporting behavior in clinical settings, which is the ultimate goal of pharmacovigilance education. Future research should address these limitations through multi-center randomized or crossover designs, direct comparisons with other active learning strategies (such as team-based learning or flipped classrooms), and longitudinal follow-up of real-world reporting behavior.

Implications and future directions:

Within the constraints noted above, our findings indicate that the jigsaw cooperative learning method is feasible and effective for early ADR education in nursing students, enhancing knowledge, skills, engagement and perceptions related to pharmacovigilance. Systematic integration of such sessions into pharmacology, nursing and patient-safety

curricula may strengthen nurses' pharmacovigilance roles and support institutional and national efforts to improve ADR reporting systems. Future studies could explore hybrid models that combine jigsaw with other evidence-based instructional approaches (e.g., flipped classroom, simulation, or case-based learning), compare different cooperative structures, and examine the long-term clinical impact of these educational strategies on ADR detection and reporting in real practice settings.

Authors' contributions:

Conception and design of the study: Jyothsnya S & Gokilavani M

Acquisition and interpretation of data: Sabari Anandh J V & Laishram Sanjana

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Revising it critically: Jyothsnya S, Gokilavani M & Sabari Anandh J V

Final approval of the manuscript version to be submitted: Jyothsnya S, Gokilavani M & Sabari Anandh J V

Declarations:

Ethics approval: SPMCH/IEC/AP/70/2026-27

Data availability: The datasets used and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author (Sabari Anandh J V) on reasonable request via email: crony.8681@gmail.com

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